

Research datasets and collections in architecture and public art (1945– 2000)

Offered in exchange for a research or teaching position

1. Introduction

This document is an academic communication in which Mr. Lochman provides descriptions of datasets on architecture and art in the architecture of the second half of the 20th century, which he may provide in exchange for a research or teaching position in higher education (university) and/or a museum. Mr. Lochman has an art collection that can also become part of a research or student project. He describes below his academic background, skills, and knowledge, datasets, and collection items offered. The best way to contact him is via his personal e-mail address: janlochman@gmail.com.

The information contained in this document may change over time, and updated versions may therefore be issued. The version number and date of issue are indicated on page 1.

2. About Jan Lochman

Jan Lochman (*1981) comes from Prague, the Czech Republic. He graduated from the Czech University of Life Sciences in Prague with a degree in agriculture management. His master's research focused on *in vitro* propagation of endangered *Mammillaria* species, aiming to develop a suitable propagation method and thus limit their decline due to illegal collection.

Later, his professional career turned to education and heritage interpretation. Since 2018, he has become more intensively involved in projects focused on heritage conservation.¹ In 2021, he started to study at Charles University, where he focused on information studies, research methodology, and data science.²

2.1. Research and teaching experience

Jan Lochman has professional experience with document, exploratory, and quantitative experimental research. He has worked as a teacher of professional subjects at a higher vocational school and has led university course exercises.

2.2. Projects and grants

Mr. Lochman gained most experience with grant projects in NGOs and as a sole project manager.

He has extensive experience in project management and grant documentation. In 2009–2010, he led a project for photo documentation of collections for Wikipedia within Wikimedia Czech Republic, where he designed the project and budget, coordinated a team of six volunteers, and was responsible for the results and the final report.³

In 2010–2020, he worked as an administrator for the *Media project*,⁴ where he assessed applications for support for volunteers documenting the countryside and other specific topics for Wikipedia.

1 Some reports for these projects might be found on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/search?q=creators.orcid%3A%220000-0003-2821-3318%22&l=list&p=1&s=50&sort=newest>.

2 More information can be found on Jan Lochman's LinkedIn page: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/jan-lochman-606a8047/>.

3 Report of a granted project *Acquiring specific types of photographs*: https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Grants:PEG/WM_CZ/Acquiring_scientific_and_specializedPictures/Report.

4 Overview of Mr. Lochman's involvement in leading and administering documentary photographic projects for Wikipedia: <https://zenodo.org/records/17871096>.

In 2021–2022, he participated in the preparation of the grant application and provided advice within the project *Photo documentation of endangered buildings and art in architecture*.⁵

In these and other projects, he usually coordinated teams of around 5–10 people and budgets of around 800–12,000 EUR. These projects yielded tens of thousands of photographs and an important memory footprint of the history of the Czech and Polish countryside, demolished buildings, and artworks.

3. Datasets

The offer includes three completed datasets and two thematic data sources.

The first dataset Mr. Lochman created as a background resource for an article on Sylva Lacinová on the Czech Wikipedia⁶ During its preparation, a research-relevant question emerged concerning the influences on this Czech sculptor, which led to a more systematic collection and structuring of the data.

The second dataset was originally developed in order to simplify the documentation of art in architecture. Subsequently, it became clear that it also represents a valuable resource for broader research into public art of the period.

The third dataset emerged more or less incidentally through the activities of members of the *Ošklivá architektura* community, who contributed data on the locations of so-called Finnish houses. Given the current surge in scholarly interest in this topic, Mr. Lochman has decided to develop this dataset further. At the moment, Mr. Lochman is analysing this dataset, and its outcome will lead to a scholarly article.

The remaining two collections represent thematic data sources and partial datasets whose integration could result, on the one hand, in a comprehensive dataset on the architecture of the second half of the 20th century and, on the other hand, in a dataset of building materials.

Most of these datasets also have an international dimension. They either directly include data from abroad or are designed so that their structure and results can be generalised by a researcher to the context of Czechoslovakia and subsequently used for comparative research with other countries. In this way, they are not limited to a purely local context but open up possibilities for international comparison and integration into broader research frameworks.

3.1. Art in architecture in Czechoslovakia (1972–1989)

3.1.1. Introduction

Art in architecture has been around for millennia. From ruler, to church, back to ruler or wealthy individuals, and then to the state, the artistic decoration of architecture changes donor.

⁵ Photodocumentation project grant request:

https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Grants:Project/Rapid/Art_Jarka/Documentation_of_endangered_buildings_and_art_works.

⁶ Available via: https://cs.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sylva_Lacinov%C3%A1

Czechoslovakia, as a state, adopted the *percent for art* programme after WWII, inspired by similar programs used to support artists and decoration of public spaces by states, which had introduced percent for art before.⁷

The percentage for the art program brought over 16,000 works of art to architecture in Czechoslovakia.⁸ However, unlike the original East Germany,⁹ these works are gradually disappearing.¹⁰

The dataset, therefore, represents important study material that can familiarize the professional public with this issue in detail and open up, important scientific questions. Although part of the original documentation of the *Czech and Slovak fund of fine arts* and their company *Dílo* is in the archives, it is not complete, and some parts of these funds remain inaccessible.¹¹

In the context of the disappearance of fine arts, this dataset constitutes a valuable source of information, the processing of which is desirable not only for the Czech environment but also for international comparison. Similar programs existed in many countries around the world, such as *Percent for art* in the US, *Kunst am Bau* in Germany, or the *Procentageregeling voor beeldende kunst* in the Netherlands.⁷

3.1.2. Dataset digitalization and publishing findings

Firstly, we had photographed *Dílo*'s yearbooks, called *Spolupráce výtvarníka s architektem* (translated into English as *Collaboration between an artist and an architect*). Next, we applied optical character recognition to extract the text from the images, producing raw text that often contained multiple errors. This output was reviewed and corrected by a human, who fixed line breaks, corrected obvious errors, and added consistent delimiters to mark different data fields. Finally, the cleaned text was programmatically parsed to split the text into records and extract individual fields into a structured format. Figure 1 shows a preview of the resulting data in a table.

Rok	Místo	Dílo	Investor	Strana
1874	Ústí nad Labem	Art protis "Vlakonoš" pro budovu KSC	KV KSC Ústí nad Labem	74
1875	Ústí nad Labem	Kovaná okna pro sístní hrad Sítokov	Správa hradu Sítokova Ústí nad Labem	74
1876	Ústí nad Labem	Směrníky z umělé hmoty pro závodní jídelnu chemický		74
1877	Ústí nad Labem	Mosazná výtvarná madla na dveře pro závodní jídelnu chemický		74
1878	Ústí nad Labem	Keramický reliéf do haly závodní jídelny chemický		74
1879	Ústí nad Labem	Tri matované vitáže (sklo a dlovo) pro salonek ředitelů a pSpolchemie Ústí nad Labem		74
1880	Ústí nad Labem	Svítlidla (sklo a mosaz) pro zasedací místnost INVA v Předlicích		74
1881	Ústí nad Labem	Dekoratívni reliéf (lity hliník) pro vstupní halu INVA v Předlicích		75
1882	Ústí nad Labem	Sklový reliéf "Symbol života" pro zasedací místnost INVA v Výrobní družstvo invalidů Litoměřice		75
1883	Ústí nad Labem	Kamenná plastika "Žena" v areálu nemocnice	Inženýrská organizace Ústí nad Labem	75
1884	Ústí nad Labem	Skleněná mozaika pro ZDS na Kamenném vrchu	Pozemní stavby Ústí nad Labem	75
1885	Ústí nad Labem	Goblén pro kancelář CKM	Cestovní kancelář mládeže Praha	75
1886	Ústí nad Labem	Dřevěný reliéf pro prodejnu květin ve Fučíkové ul.	Zahradnický podnik Ústí nad Labem	75
12034	Ústí nad Labem	Označení 36 provozoven ve Fučíkové ulici	Pozemní stavby, Ústí n. L., Velká Hradeb 120	120
12035	Ústí nad Labem	Znak restaurace a kavárny "Merkur", hotel "Vladimir" ve Fučíkové ulici	Restaurace, Ústí n. L., Palíšská 20	120
12036	Ústí nad Labem	Označení pivnice "Družba", Fučíková 86	Restaurace, Ústí n. L., Palíšská 20	120
12037	Ústí nad Labem	Skleněná mozaika v hale tělocvičny TJ Rudé hvězdy v ulici Krájská správa ministerstva vnitra, Ústí n. L.	Krájská správa ministerstva vnitra, Ústí n. L.	121
12038	Ústí nad Labem	Plastika "Gymnastika" - sádra, díveo - ve vstupní hale tělocvičny TJ Rudé hvězdy v ulici Krájská správa ministerstva vnitra, Ústí n. L.	Krájská správa ministerstva vnitra, Ústí n. L.	121
12039	Ústí nad Labem	Plastika "boxer" - hliník, mosaz - na schodišti tělocvičny TJ Rudé hvězdy v ulici Krájská správa ministerstva vnitra, Ústí n. L.	Krájská správa ministerstva vnitra, Ústí n. L.	121
12040	Ústí nad Labem	Plastická skleněná vitáž ve vstupní hale Krájského projekt. Pozemní stavby, Ústí n. L., Velká Hradeb 121	Pozemní stavby, Ústí n. L., Velká Hradeb 121	121
12041	Ústí nad Labem	Plastický zvířat - umělé pryskyřice - "Dětský svět" v Zoo Ústí+Zoologická zahrada, Ústí n. L., Svermova 121	Zoo Ústí nad Labem, Ústí n. L., Svermova 121	121
12042	Ústí nad Labem	Návrhy na firemní označení prodejen: Hedva, Klenoty, Bžď, Hedva, Moravská Třebová, Fučíkova 19+121	Prodeje, Ústí n. L., Fučíkova 19+121	121
12043	Ústí nad Labem	Pískovcová socha "Nový život" před střediskem občanské vřizenyřské organizace, Ústí n. L., ulice 5p 122	Občanská vřizenyřská organizace, Ústí n. L., ulice 5p 122	122
12044	Ústí nad Labem	Triptych "Historie bojů dělnické třídy" - olej na plátně - ve foyeru budovy Krájské policie školy v Hoř. 122	Policejní škola, Ústí n. L., Hoř. 122	122
12045	Ústí nad Labem	Triptych "Vystavba socialistické společnosti" - olej na plátně - ve foyeru přednáškového sálu Krájské 122	Přednáškový sál, Ústí n. L., Krájské 122	122

Figure 1: Screenshot of the dataset table

7 Pavel Karous, "Umění v hotelu ČSSR. Systém osazování výtvarného umění v architektuře na Západě a v ČSSR," in *Hotel Praha* (Bigg Boss, 2019). In Czech.

8 Jan Lochman, *Database of the Collaboration between an Artist and an Architect* (2023), 6, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10149620>.

9 In the article *Long in the tooth*, Anna-Sophie Laug suggests that the owners of German art in architecture approach this art responsibly and take care of it. It is rare for the art to have to be removed and moved to a depository, but more often it is kept in place or moved with the owner. Anna-Sophie Laug, "Long in the Tooth: The Maintenance, Preservation and Loss of Art in Architecture," in *70 Years of Art in Architecture in Germany* (Deutscher Kunstverlag, 2021).

10 The statistics for the Czech Republic are unknown. However, a review of the dataset, a review of sculptor Sylva Lacinová's work, and interviews with other enthusiasts of mapping art in architecture show that many works, especially those located in the offices of former state-owned enterprises and on the walls and facades of houses, have already been lost or destroyed. Our own rescue operations, in which we removed several reliefs at our own expense and are now looking for a new home for them, indicate how different the understanding of the role of a good steward is in the Czech Republic.

11 Vladislava Říhová and Zuzana Křenková, *Archivní fondy podniku Českého fondu výtvarných umění Dílo*, 65, no. 2 (2016): 104–119. In Czech.

During the processing of printed periodicals, we became so familiar with them that we published these results in a report titled *Database of the Collaboration between an artist and an architect*, which is available in the Zenodo repository.¹²

3.1.3. Towards the manuscript and future direction of research

After digitizing periodicals, we were able to use them in daily life to quickly find information about an artwork or filter for works by a specific artist. We had also performed faceting, receiving information on types of artworks or materials used. These findings, together with the recommendation for future research on the dataset, could form the basis of a manuscript. This exploratory article will provide a first look at art in the architecture of the 1970s and 1980s, and may open new research questions.

From the initial semi-quantitative evaluation of the dataset, it is clear that, for further quantitative analysis, the dataset needs to be cleaned and duplicates removed. We investigated the frequency of multiplications in a multistrata selected sample and concluded that 5–15% of observations are duplicates. Their presence is blocking a rigorous evaluation of the dataset and an understanding of this field of heritage.

3.1.4. Related datasets and works

As mentioned above, we use the dataset regularly to search for information on artworks and artists. The dataset of 16.836 lines was transferred to Google Sheets and is available online, but is not public, as private funds funded the digitalization process. Working actively with the datasets yields findings that we may use in future data cleaning.

In addition, we created a dataset of works by the sculptor Sylva Lacinová (fig. 2), including photographs of works by her potential influencers. This dataset can thus serve as comparative material with the Collaboration dataset, since it is based on other sources of information. We can also use it for our own research into the influences on this sculptor. The influence might be her teacher, Vicent Makovský, or British sculptor Henry Moore.

Figure 2: Supposed localizations of Sylva Lacinová's artworks. Blue – exterior, red – interior

3.2. Buildings erected in 1945–2000

The dataset does not exist yet, but the data are available as shown below. The aim of creating this dataset is twofold: to support research opportunities and to present the department's work to the general public, making the data accessible for their use.

¹² Available via: <https://zenodo.org/records/10149620>.

3.2.1. Data sources

There are three primary sources of data for the dataset: smaller datasets, the *Ošklivá architektura* Facebook group, and the architecture book collection. The most important value for the first two sources is location, characterized by geographic coordinates or the name of the municipality. The second most frequent value for these two sources are photographs. The importance of the last source lies in the specific information, such as construction years or architects, which can enhance the data from the two previous sources.

3.2.1.1. Smaller datasets

Smaller datasets contain locations within various municipalities (towns) in Central Europe. There are also datasets of endangered buildings, buildings opened during different events, etc. All are in Mr. Lochman's possessions, primarily in digital tabs and maps. With particular manual or programmatic effort, these can be unified into a master set. There are 23 such datasets, including about 1060 items.

Another category of the datasets is Mr. Lochman's collection of photographs of buildings located on the disks in his possession or online, mainly in the Wikimedia Commons repository. As many locations are identified and organized into location-descriptive categories or directories, this dataset may also help improve the master set. Actually, it counts about 756 identified locations and thousands of photographs.

3.2.1.2. Facebook group

The other source of data might be the Facebook group called *Ošklivá architektura*¹³ (translated to English as Ugly architecture). It is a group for connecting with architecture built between 1945 and 2000. It contains posts from members of buildings in the Czech Republic, Slovakia, and other countries. Each post includes a location, identified by the municipality's name, and photographs. Other data are optional. Some contributors are prone to providing their data for such a database, which would be publicly available to others. Mr. Lochman's contribution to the group is much bigger than that of the previously mentioned datasets, so these data could also be freely used for the master set. Data of other users is covered by copyright. Retrieving the data would require both manual and programmatic approaches, and would need more human labor than creating a master set from the previously mentioned datasets.

3.2.1.3. Architecture book collection

The last big resource of information is Mr. Lochman's architecture library, which includes about 100 books. This collection is partially digitized, with the process ongoing (fig. 3). The value is that it provides more information about the buildings. The dataset might be used as an occasional reference source for specific information, but not as a mass information source, which copyright laws prohibits.

Figure 3: Part of the collection of popular science publications that has been scanned

13 Available via: <https://www.facebook.com/groups/OsklivaArchitektura>.

3.2.2. Towards the database, Wikibase tests

We have been considering various ways to create the database. After multiple tests, we have decided to use Wikibase as the best solution,¹⁴ which provides multiple ways to consume and contribute data. The biggest challenge on this platform was developing the data model. In the end, we decided to use less specific descriptions so that everyone could contribute without needing to consult an extensive dictionary. The question is still: how to model, for example, location duplets across countries? However, for future stable use and development, Mr. Lochman recommends moving the data away from the cloud to standalone Wikibase installation, as being in the cloud has multiple drawbacks, which may endanger the development of the database and its project.

3.2.3. Related datasets

Some specific datasets may stand alone and serve a specific research, or may be included in the master set. The first consists of wooden-panel houses, which, at their base, are not considered architecture; the second is a datasource for preworked building materials.

3.2.3.1. Finnish houses

Finnish houses dataset (fig. 4) consists of wooden prefabricated houses, mostly deployed in the 1940s and 1950s across central Europe. Some of them are of Scandinavian origin, some are not, but they form a specific category because the general public, as well as maps, considers these houses to be of Finnish or Swedish origin.

Currently, this dataset, containing about 200 clusters of buildings of this type in the Czech Republic, Poland, and Slovakia, is being analyzed and will lead to a paper on the categorization of mass-produced wooden houses in the 1940s, 1950s, and 1960s. Such a classification could provide valuable insight into cross-border architecture sharing and a basis for further research in this area, as it clearly identifies, based on easily detectable visual features, different types of buildings that, in reality, correspond to different models from different manufacturers. Such a classification can then simplify subsequent research, whether historical, sociological, or other. Of course, it will also provide a valuable basis for heritage conservation, including what stands, how much of it still stands, and its condition.

Figure 4: The map represents the Finnish houses dataset, specifically the occurrence of colonies of these houses in the Czech Republic and their size, according to the number of individual houses in each colony

3.2.3.2. Building materials

The second valuable resource is of building materials, such as glass bricks, steel-aluminium doors and windows, or concrete pots, which architects used in architecture, especially in the 1960s to 1980s in Czechoslovakia. This data consists of localized photographs from the Czech Republic, Germany, or Spain. Most of these photographs, Mr. Lochman curates on Wikimedia Commons.

¹⁴ See an example: <https://web.archive.org/web/20251008133258/https://uglyarchitecture.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q1>

This dataset can support research into the influence of building materials across west and Eastern Europe. That is, where those influences flowed from and where, and in what way.

3.2.4. Possible research

Research from an architecture dataset might include visual comparisons, highlighting similar buildings around the world, and research into the influences between architects.

From various sources, we know that Czech architects were drawing on what was being built around the world and trying similar adaptations locally. On the other hand, the visual comparison may point to architects who were not inspired abroad and who were building their own designs.

An example of an influence could be thin-shell structures or suspended roofs, which were built worldwide before World War II but apparently only reached Bohemia after World War II. Another example could be houses suspended from a central pylon.

The results of the research can provide a valuable understanding of the influence of global architecture on Eastern European architecture, particularly socialist modernism.

Another possible area of research could examine the hypothesis that the representation of socialist modernism in Czechia differs from that in other parts of the Eastern Bloc.

4. Collection items

The collection of items mostly complements the above datasets. For example, for the dataset of Sylva Lacinová's works, Mr. Lochman secured her drawings and sculptures from early childhood through all phases of her professional life until her death. It is similar to the dataset of building materials, which stores samples. These collections can serve as an illustrative material for research or for organizing thematic exhibitions such as the one titled *Henry Moore's influence on Eastern European artists*.

In addition, Mr. Lochman has some works of art that he saved as part of the *Art preservation in architecture program*. These include, for example, works by Stanislav Holý (fig. 5), which we saved in 2024¹⁵ and which can serve as a basis for research in the field of restoration of works on modern materials or for exhibitions.

Restoration of works of art on modern materials is a poorly documented topic in the academy¹⁶ and therefore, there is a lack of materials for professional schools and future restorers. Publishing case studies on removing works, cleaning, and cleaning from hazardous materials can thus clarify innovative methods of restoration work for both academics and students.

Figure 5: One of Stanislav Holý's rescued works after re-composition

15 Jan Lochman, "Removal and cleaning of two artworks made out of tiles," Zenodo, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13786053>.

16 Marta T. Mendes et al., *In Situ Preservation and Restoration of Architectural Tiles, Materials and Procedures: Results of an International Survey*, 2015.

From the perspective of exhibition design, the rescued works are suitable for exhibitions such as the *Regional interpretation of Sesame Street*. The author of the rescued works, Stanislav Holý, created characters and decorations for the series *Studio Kamarád* for Czechoslovak Television and was inspired by American television series Sesame Street. His works for architecture depict these characters and decorations, and the situation is no different in the case of the rescued reliefs.

The above works are not cultural monuments from a legal perspective, but in the case of export, it would be advisable to request clarification.